

FATIGUE LIFE PREDICTION METHOD FOR COMPOSITES UNDER SPECTRUM LOADING

Bao Rui, Zhang Jianyu

School of Aeronautic Science and Technology, Beijing University of Aeronautics and Aeronautics, Beijing, 100083, PR China

SUMMARY: This paper presented a model that can be used to predict fatigue life of composite structures under spectrum loading. The primary objective in building the model was to develop a method with which constant amplitude fatigue study achievements can be used while dealing with the circumstances of structures subjected to arbitrary load spectrum. The bases of the model are residual-strength-degradation approach and Miner's rule. The key points of the method is: description function of residual strength degradation, definition of damage caused by each constant amplitude load segment and its accumulation rules, randomness description way of residual strength and the dispersivity of fatigue life. Two kinds of distribution of fatigue life i.e. lognormal distribution and two-parameter distribution are discussed in detail. The method could be applied to fatigue life prediction as well as durability and reliability analysis of composite structures under time-variant loading, which can provide considerable results for structural designers at a macro level.

KEYWORDS: fatigue life, residual strength, spectrum loading, reliability of composites

INTRODUCTION

The growing use of composite materials on aircraft structures has led to many technical challenges. One is predicting fatigue life especially under spectrum loading. For this prediction, it is imperative to know how and when a structure will fail. Composite materials exhibit complex failure mechanisms under fatigue conditions. The four basic failure modes are fiber breakage, matrix cracking, and interfacial debonding and ply delamination. Existing life prediction techniques used for composite materials can be categorized as follows: Macro-mechanic, Micro-mechanic, Degradation and Probabilistic^[1]. The macroscopic methodology is simple and based on accepted failure criteria. It provides a general engineering solution and has attracted considerable attention of the structural designers whose interest is only in those properties that manifest themselves at a macro level. In this methodology one may either pursue the residual-strength-degradation or modulus-degradation approaches.

The residual-strength-degradation model is based on the theory that fatigue damage of the composites is accumulating with the increasing of the number of loading cycles, which lead to the deterioration of residual strength. Failure will occur when the residual strength drops to the peak value of the load. It is assumed that the residual strength was a monotonically decreasing function of the number of loading cycles. This model is applicable to a variety of materials, layups and loadings.

The composite structures of modern aircraft will be subjected to different load spectra as the changes of operational use. Also, different users may use the aircraft in different ways, again resulting in different load spectra. The large number of load spectra makes testing very expensive and predicting lifetime much difficult. Therefore, there is a need to develop a

theory with which constant amplitude fatigue data can be used to predict the fatigue life of an arbitrary load spectrum^[2].

This paper puts emphasis on the residual-strength-degradation model and extends it to the application of predicting fatigue life of composites under spectrum loading. The way to consider the randomness during the process is also discussed.

MODEL

In the residual-strength-degradation approach, failure is considered to occur when the residual strength decreases to the level of maximum applied stress. Figure 1 shows the whole degradation procedure under random loading, and the figure makes it easily understood that the fatigue life of composites under a certain load-time course is not deterministic.

Fig.1 Residual strength model of fatigue life

Consider a composite component subjected to constant amplitude loading, the residual strength $X(n)$ initially equals the static strength $X(0)$, and is assumed to decrease monotonically. If environmental and frequency-based effects are ignored, the general form of the assumed residual strength relation may be written as^[3]:

$$X^c(n) = X^c(0) - f(S, \omega, R)n^v \quad (1)$$

Where, $X(0)$ is initial static strength, c and v are both yet-to-be-determined strength deterioration parameters, $f(S, \omega, R)$ describes the rate of strength loss associated with cyclic loading, and here, S is the peak stress magnitude of the loading, R is the stress ratio, ω is stress frequency.

Assumed that ω , R are constants, the maximum stress is S , and the corresponding fatigue life is N , then Equation (1) can be simplified:

$$X^c(n) = X^c(0) - f(S)n^v \quad (2)$$

The function $f(S)$ in Equation (2) is determined by the aforementioned failure criterion. Based on the theory, when failure occurs, the residual strength $X(n)$ equals the peak stress S and the number of loading cycles n equals the fatigue life N . Then we have

$$f(S) = \frac{X^c(0) - S^c}{N^\nu} \quad (3)$$

Substituting Equation (3) into Equation (2)

$$X^c(n) = X^c(0) - [X^c(0) - S^c](n/N)^\nu \quad (4)$$

The damage after n cycles of this constant amplitude loading can be defined as follows:

$$D = n/N = \left[(X^c(0) - X^c(n)) / (X^c(0) - S^c) \right]^{1/\nu} \quad (5)$$

It is easily seen that when failure occurs,

$$\begin{aligned} n &= N \\ D &= 1 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

For aircraft usage, a more significant thing is to know how to deal with the randomly-ordered loading circumstance. The generalized methodology is to assume that the loading spectrum is comprised of a series of constant amplitude segments, and Miner's linear damage summation rule is adopted. The basic assumption of Miner's rule is that failure occurs when the accumulated damage $D = 1$. If load spectra can be simplified into m blocks, and each of them is a constant amplitude segment, then the damage of the i th block is:

$$D_i = n_i / N_i \quad (7)$$

Where, n_i is the acted cycle of the constant amplitude loading in block i and N_i is the fatigue life under this constant amplitude loading. So, the damage of the load spectra is:

$$D_s = \sum_{i=1}^m D_i = \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{n_i}{N_i} \quad (8)$$

And the fatigue life of the composite component under this spectrum loading i.e. the acting number of the load spectra is:

$$N = \frac{1}{D_s} \quad (9)$$

All the work to predict fatigue life of composites under spectrum loading is simplified to get the fatigue damage of each block of the load spectra. As discussed above, D_i can be described as follows:

$$D_i = \left[(X_i^{c_i}(0) - X_i^{c_i}(n_i)) / (X_i^{c_i}(0) - S^{c_i}) \right]^{1/\nu_i} \quad (10)$$

Where,

$$X_i(0) = \left\{ X_{i-1}^{c_{i-1}}(0) - \left[X_{i-1}^{c_{i-1}}(0) - S^{c_{i-1}} \right] \left(n_{i-1} / N_{i-1} \right)^{v_{i-1}} \right\}^{1/c_{i-1}} \quad (11)$$

This process of residual strength degradation can be sketched by fig.2.

Fig.2 Sketch map of residual strength degradation under spectrum loading

The discussion above is deterministic, and do not incorporate the uncertainties in the values of the parameters that affect fatigue life. Whereas reliability analysis plays a greatly important part especially in aircraft structures' design and evaluation, probabilistic methods must be available, which rationally treat the randomness in the parameters and compute the reliability. The randomness of fatigue life mostly comes from the uncertainties in the material properties and loading. For the practical problem, structures are subjected to time-variant loading, and not only the number of cycles but also the stress/stain amplitudes are random. In the material property aspect, for the complexity of the failure mechanism and the randomness of the crack initiation and crack growth, the relationship of residual strength and loading cycles could not be deterministic.

The concern of this study is the fatigue life of a given composite component subjected to a certain spectrum loading. So, here the numbers of cycles of different loading stress are not considered as random variables. Neglecting the scatter of initial static strength, the dispersivity of the residual strength is mostly caused by random factors in cyclic process. Therefore, the residual strength is the secondary variables, the randomness of which comes form the uncertainties in the rate of strength loss described by $f(S)$ in Equation (2).

A randomized form of Equation (2) can be described as:

$$X^c(n) = X^c(0) - Y(n) f(S) n^v \quad (12)$$

Where, $Y(n)$ is a stochastic process. There is two extreme cases existing for this stochastic process, one is that the two arbitrary different times are completely uncorrelated, which is usually called white noise process, and the other is that two arbitrary different times are completely correlated, the random process $Y(n)$ will be treated as a random variable Y , then

the stochastic process model presented by Equation (12) will be changed into a random variable model. The dispersivity of the results gained by random variable model is the maximum, so it is conservative and can be adopted in solving engineering problems.

And till now, we obtained a simplified function of residual-strength-random-decreasing and the number of loading cycles as shown in Equation (13).

$$X^c(n) = X^c(0) - Y^v \left[X^c(0) - S^c \right] (n/N)^v \quad (13)$$

Moreover, knowledge of the statistical distribution of residual strength and life would be more useful in practical applications. We can assume that both residual strength distribution after an arbitrary load history, and the life distribution under constant amplitude fatigue, may be represented by lognormal distribution functions or by two parameter Weibull functions. These two cases will be discussed respectively in the following. No matter what distribution functions are considered, the fatigue damage of the i th block can be described as:

$$D_i = \frac{1}{Y_i} \left[\frac{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - X_i^{c_i}(n_i))}{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - S^{c_i})} \right]^{1/\nu_i} \quad (14)$$

And fatigue life N

$$N = \frac{1}{D_s} = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^m D_i} = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ \frac{1}{Y_i} \left[\frac{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - X_i^{c_i}(n_i))}{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - S^{c_i})} \right]^{1/\nu_i} \right\}} \quad (15)$$

For further study, a predigestion is necessary. The dispersivity of damage caused by each block would be considered to be the same, or the largest dispersivity of all the blocks would be adopted in the predicting, then Y_i is replaced by Y' and Equation (15) could be rewritten as:

$$N = Y' \cdot \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ \left[\frac{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - X_i^{c_i}(n_i))}{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - S^{c_i})} \right]^{1/\nu_i} \right\}} \quad (16)$$

Where,

$$\sigma(Y') = \max \{ \sigma(Y_i) \} \quad (17)$$

If lognormal function is assumed to represent the distribution of residual strength or fatigue life, the logarithm conversion of equation (16) is:

$$\lg N = \lg Y' - \lg \sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ \left[\frac{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - X_i^{c_i}(n_i))}{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - S^{c_i})} \right]^{1/\nu_i} \right\} \quad (18)$$

That is

$$N' = Y'' - \lg \sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ \left[\frac{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - X_i^{c_i}(n_i))}{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - S^{c_i})} \right]^{1/\nu_i} \right\} \quad (19)$$

Where, $N' = \lg N$, $Y'' = \lg Y'$. Y'' is a normal random variable, the mean value of which can be assumed reasonably to be zero. The standard deviation of log-fatigue-life N' is the same with that of Y'' .

If block j is considered to have the largest dispersivity, Y_j will be gotten by a series of test. For the feasibility of test data analysis, Equation (13) would be changed into the following form:

$$\frac{X_j^{c_j}(0) - X_j^{c_j}(n_j)}{X_j^{c_j}(0) - S_j^{c_j}} = Y_j^{\nu_j} \left(\frac{n_j}{N_j} \right) \quad (20)$$

The logarithm conversion of Equation (20) is

$$Z = \lg \left(\frac{n_j}{N_j} \right) + H \quad (21)$$

Where,

$$Z = \frac{1}{\nu_j} \lg \left(\frac{X_j^{c_j}(0) - X_j^{c_j}(n_j)}{X_j^{c_j}(0) - S_j^{c_j}} \right) \quad (22)$$

$$H = \lg Y_j$$

Consider having the following data as shown in table 1 and Figure 3 via experiments,

Table 1 data necessary for analysis

Load	Material properties	Test data residual strength
S, R, ω	$X(0), N_j, c_j, \nu_j$	$X_1(n_j), \dots, X_k(n_j)$

Fig.3 Sketch map of test data

Then we have

$$s_H = s_Z = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{l=1}^k (Z_l - \bar{Z}_l)^2}{k-2}} \quad (23)$$

Where,

$$Z_l = \frac{1}{v_j} \lg \left(\frac{X^{c_j}(0) - X_i^{c_j}(n_j)}{X^{c_j}(0) - S^{c_j}} \right) \quad (24)$$

$$\bar{Z}_l = \lg \left(\frac{n_j}{N_j} \right)$$

So, it can be considered reasonably that

$$\hat{\sigma}(\lg N) = s_H \quad (25)$$

Thus, we can get the normal function to represent the distribution of log-fatigue-life N' .

$$f(n') = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{n' - \mu}{\sigma} \right)^2 \right\} \quad (26)$$

Where,

$$\mu = -\lg \sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ \left[\frac{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - X_i^{c_i}(n_i))}{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - S^{c_i})} \right]^{1/v_i} \right\} \quad (27)$$

$$\sigma = s_H$$

The probability of failure may be expressed as

$$P(N < n) = P(\lg N < n') = \int_0^{n'} f(x) dx \quad (28)$$

To different survival probability p_k ,

$$N_{p_k} = y'_{p_k} \cdot \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ \left[\frac{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - X_i^{c_i}(n_i))}{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - S^{c_i})} \right]^{1/v_i} \right\}} \quad (29)$$

Where,

$$y'_{p_k} = y_{j p_k} = 10^{u_{p_k} \cdot s_H} \quad (30)$$

And u_{p_k} is the p_k percentile of standard normal distribution. The distribution function of fatigue life is:

$$F_N(n) = \int_0^n \frac{1}{\ln 10 \cdot x \cdot \sigma \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\lg x - \mu}{\sigma} \right)^2 \right\} dx \quad (31)$$

Where, μ and σ is shown in Equation (27).

If two-parameter Weibull function is assumed to represent the distribution of residual strength or fatigue life, we might as well assume that the distribution of random variable Y may also be represented by two parameter Weibull functions in Equation (32).

$$F_Y(y) = 1 - \exp \left[-\left(\frac{y}{\beta} \right)^\alpha \right] \quad (32)$$

Where β is the scale factor, which represent the 63.2 percentile of the distribution, and α is the shape factor, which describes the degree of scatter of the data. Both the shape and scale parameters may be obtained from experimental results using maximum likelihood method.

Then,

$$y_{p_k} = \beta \cdot \left[-\ln(1 - p_k) \right]^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \quad (33)$$

And

$$N_{p_k} = y_{p_k} \cdot \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ \left[\frac{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - X_i^{c_i}(n_i))}{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - S^{c_i})} \right]^{1/\nu_i} \right\}} \quad (34)$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned} P(N < n) &= P \left(Y < n \sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ \left[\frac{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - X_i^{c_i}(n_i))}{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - S^{c_i})} \right]^{1/\nu_i} \right\} \right) \\ &= F_Y \left(n \sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ \left[\frac{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - X_i^{c_i}(n_i))}{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - S^{c_i})} \right]^{1/\nu_i} \right\} \right) \\ &= 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{n \sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ \left[\frac{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - X_i^{c_i}(n_i))}{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - S^{c_i})} \right]^{1/\nu_i} \right\}}{\beta} \right)^\alpha \right] \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

The distribution function of fatigue life can be obtained as shown in Equation (36).

$$F_N(n) = 1 - \exp \left[-\left(\frac{n}{\beta'} \right)^\alpha \right] \quad (36)$$

Where

$$\beta' = \frac{\beta}{\sum_{i=1}^m \left\{ \left[\frac{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - X_i^{c_i}(n_i))}{(X_i^{c_i}(0) - S^{c_i})} \right]^{1/\nu_i} \right\}} \quad (37)$$

Considering the dispersivity of initial static strength $X(0)$, of which the distribution function is $F_{X_0}(x)$. The randomness of initial faults and damage growth can be deemed as independent, thus

$$\begin{aligned} P(N < n, X(0) < x_0) &= P(N < n)P(X(0) < x_0) \\ &= F_N(n) \cdot F_{X_0}(x_0) \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

SUMMARY

A residual-strength-degradation-based model is presented in this paper, which can be applied to fatigue life prediction and reliability analysis for composite structures subjected to random-ordered loading spectra. The basic assumption of this model is

1. The complex loading spectrum comprise of a series of constant amplitude segments.
2. For each segment, residual-strength-degradation model can be used to describe the fatigue performance, and lots of achievements under constant amplitude loading for the composites studied have been gained.
3. Damage is defined by the ratio of loading cycles and the mean value of fatigue life under this loading case. The fatigue damage accumulated, and the accumulation can be expressed by Miner's linear damage summation rule.

Then an expression of fatigue life for composites components subjected to spectrum loading is established in the paper.

For reliability analysis, the fatigue life prediction expression is randomized, and some simplification is done for practical problems. A random-variable model is presented, by which the fatigue life with certain survival probability of a given composites can be predicted. Lognormal distribution and two-parameter Weibull distribution, which is widely used to represent the distribution of fatigue life and residual strength, are discussed in detail. Based on these discussions, the two forms of distribution functions of fatigue life and the determination method of the parameters in the functions are given.

At last, the way to consider the dispersivity of initial static strength as well as that of residual strength degradation is also mentioned.

The method presented in this paper provides considerable results for structural designers at a macro level, and could be applied to fatigue life prediction as well as durability and reliability analysis of composite structures under spectrum loading.

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